

The Influence of The Problem Based Learning (PBL) Model on Learning Outcomes of Class IV Students on Subtema 2 Diversity in Kebersaman SDN 091254 Batu Onom T.A 2023/2024

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A R Q I C L E I N F O

ABSTRACT

Keywords : *Problem Based Learning (PBL)* model , learning outcomes , SDN 091254 Batu Onom

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Study This aim For know is influence of learning models *Problem Based Learning (PBL)* towards results Study student class IV in subtheme 2 togetherness in diversity SDN 091254 Batu Onom . Type of research This that is study quantitative use _ method pre-experiment with form *one group pretest-posttest design* . Which became sample study This is student class IV, totaling 30 students . Instruments used is pretest and posttest tests have been carried out validation and reliability tests were carried out . The research results at the 0.05 level show that exists influence of learning models *Problem Based Learning (PBL)* to results Study student class IV in subtheme 2 togetherness in diversity of SDN 191254 Batu Onom . Can be seen that results comparison of pretest and posttest sig value is 0.000 which is significant more small from value 0.05, and t has value 16,327. It means there is influence the learning model *Problem Based Learning (PBL)* to results learn . Change results Study taught students _ with using a learning model *Problem Based Learning (PBL)* makes it difficult student active think , understand The material presented increases the sense of desire know student in seek and find information itself , compared with taught students _ without using a learning model *Problem Based Learning (PBL)*.

Keywords : *Problem Based Learning (PBL)* model , results learn , SDN 091254 Batu Onom

INTRODUCTION

Education is experience Study along life in all impacting environments and situations _ positive for development individual . That education taking place during throughout life . Teaching in understanding area is also a an activity process teach , and implement learning That bisater so in the environment wherever and whenever (Amirin:2013:4). In law about system education No.20 of 2003, said that education is a “ business aware and accomplished For realize atmosphere learning and learning for participants educate in a way active develop potency himself For own strength spiritual religion , control self , personality , intelligence , morals glorious as well as necessary skills _ himself and society ”.

By literal meaning of education is education carried out by a person teacher to participant education , expected by adults in children For Can give example modeling , learning , directing , and improving ethics , as well dig knowledge every individual . Teaching given to participants _ educate No just from formal education carried out by the holder power , however in matter This function family as well as it's the community that matters important and becoming receptacle coaching that can awaken as well as develop knowledge as well as understanding (Ab Marisyah1, Firman2, 2019).

Learning thematic or blended learning is integrated learning _ a number of theme For give experience meaningful for child . In learning Teachers have to do this too capable build units per topic . Learning thematic really needs it inner teacher creativity selection and development topic learning . Selected subjects __ should based on the environment place stay student so that learning become alive or not stiff .

According to Ministry of National Education (Trianto , 2011: 147) in question with “ learning thematic basically _ is is a learning model integrated with use theme For hook a number of eye lesson so that can give experience meaningful learning _ to students ”. Learning thematic is holistic and inclusive learning _ so that can developing aspect knowledge , attitudes and skills students , learning This use close themes _ with life student so that learning become more meaningful Because student seek and find Alone what are they learn .

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Framework conceptual is something connection between draft One with other concepts . _ Framework conceptual This useful For connect something topic to be discussed . Based on from results observations that have been made carried out in class IV at SD Negeri 091254 Batu Onom then found _ A problem that results Study student there masuk classified medium . The reason is that the teacher hasn't yet passive using innovative learning models . _ In teacher learning more tend use method lecture that makes participant educate become bored .

In activities learning need change How The method teach . For example Can just changing the conventional model into a Problem Based Learning (PBL) model which participant educate will Study solve problem with method individual nor group . For reach results Study participant educate researcher do a pretest first formerly form choice double and stuffing For know ability participant educate . Then researchers will carry out the Problem Based Learning (PBL) learning model . Then researchers will do posttest to participant educate with Same question for _ _ know does the Problem Based Learning (PBL) model provide influence to results Study participant educate . After That researcher will compare mark from pretest and posttest For get conclusion from study this .

Figure 1. Framework Conceptual

METHODS

Type of research used is study quantitative method experiment . According to Sugiyono (2016: 72) research experiment is method used _ For look for influence treatment certain towards others within controlled conditions . _ The type of research that will be used is pre-experiment with use the “One Group Design Prerest -posttest” design depicted as following :

Pretest	Treatment	Posttest
O ₁	X	O ₂

Figure 1 One-Group Pretest-Posttest Design

Information

- O₁ = pretest score
- O₂ = posttest score
- X = treatment given

Population is the area of generalization that consists on object / subject that has qualities and characteristics certain conditions are determined by the researcher For studied and then withdrawn conclusion (Sugiyono , 2016: 80). Population No always about people , objects and things natural others . So population in study This is all over student Class IV of SD Negeri 091254 Batu Onom .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

On research this is a trial instrument carried out on students class IV SD Negeri 091254 Jl. Asahan , km.06 Batu Onom , totaling 30 students . Instruments in study This covers test choice double For measure results Study students , trial result data instrument consists of 40 items matter . Before do study moreover formerly validity tests , reliability tests , level tests are carried out difficulty , power test differentiator , then analyzed the data with N-gain and anova tests .

Test instrument

1. Validity test

A instruments is said to be valid when $r_{count} > r_{tabel}$ and if invalid then $r_{hitung} > r_{tabel}$ of 40 questions after being tested by the instrument in other schools there are 26 valid questions and there are 14 questions not valid, until the spread is question by sum valid statements of 25 questions .

2. Reliability Test

Reliability test question aim For see decision tool the in evaluate what it evaluates . In case This observe How decision every item question in evaluate or test abilities and knowledge students . Based on reliability test results with the Kr25 model then coefficient correlation his is $0.921 < r_{11} < 1.00$ so its interpretation including in range high value . _ Then can concluded that data _ stated reliable .

3. Test Difficulty Level

Test level difficulty done For see level difficulty every question that has been share and determine is question the too easy or too difficult . that category easy question _ a total of 23 questions (1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 11, 18, 20, 21, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 30, 31, 32, 35, 36, 38, 39, 40) , category medium problem _ there are 17 questions (4,6, 7, 9, 10, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 19, 22, 29, 33, 34, 37).

4. Discriminating Power Test

Tests carried out with computing coefficient between distribution score scale That himself , who has classification Power differentiator questions that are very bad , bad , fair , good , or very good . Category not enough There are 8 questions , categories Good There are 23 questions , categories Good once 2 questions , categories just 7 questions , too category 1 question is bad .

Data Analysis

Discussion

Study This carried out at SD Negeri 091254 Batu Onom FY 2023/2024. Researcher give treatment with using the Problem Based Learning learning model in lessons during researcher do research . Researcher moreover formerly do a test run instruments in class IV at SD Negeri 096915 Perumnas Batu VI, for determine level validity , level difficulty , power The difference is , pretest and posttest , N-Gain and T-test. Researcher provides 40 questions , when testing was carried out instrument question there is the results were 26 valid questions and 14 invalid questions , so only 25 valid questions were used _ as pretest and posttest . At the moment level test is

carried out difficulty there is easy question _ as many as 23 items , medium as many as 17 items , and difficult as many as 0 items matter . At the moment power test is carried out differentiator there is not enough as many as 8, enough as many as 7, good as many as 23, and good very as many as 2. After That researcher do research at SD Negeri 091254 Batu Onom in class IV, which is ongoing for 2 weeks namely September 25 to 07 October 2023, type study use one group pretest posttest design .

Researcher give a pretest first formerly unique know ability beginning student before did it treatment during the learning process teach taking place with using the Problem Based Learning learning model . The results obtained _ student class IV with an average score of 42.20. After researcher get pretest scores , then researcher using the Problem Based Learning learning model for carry out treatment during learning . After do treatment with use posttest to students , and results posttest show that average student score class IV is 78.93.

First A data normality test is carried out which tests the normality of this data using SPSS version 26 with significance > 0.05 , the normality test results obtained were 0.029 of the data is said to be normal because $0.029 > 0.05$ after normality test was carried out furthermore Homogeneity test was carried out with the specified criteria , significance > 0.05 , was obtained mark significant 0.714 then said that what was tested was homogeneous because $0.714 > 0.05$, after the homogeneity test furthermore The N-Gain test was carried out with a score of 62.23 information Enough effective , next t-test was carried out , it was obtained tcount = 16.327 with level significance 0.000 probability significant < 0.05 , tcount $>$ ttable = $16.327 > 2.054$ then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted . Explanation This show that there is the influence of the Problem Based Learning model on results Study student on theme 1 " Beautiful Togetherness " subtheme 2 " Togetherness in Diversity " learning 1 and 2 of SD Negeri 091254 Batu Onom FY 2023/2024.

CONCLUSION

Conclusions

Based on results research and data obtained researcher during study ongoing , researcher can conclude that the use of the Problem Based Learning (PBL) learning model has an influence significant to results Study student class IV in subtheme 2 togetherness in diversity of SD Negeri 091254 Batu Onom FY 2023/2024. This thing proven with results obtained _ researcher , where student class IV obtained The average score is 42.20 on the pretest and the average score is 78.93 on the posttest. With The N-Gan test results scored 62.23 while the t-test was obtained tcount = 16.327 with level significant 0.000 probability significant < 0.05 tcount $>$ ttable = $16.327 > 0.396$ then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted . So that can concluded that there is influence use of the Problem Based Learning (PBL) learning model towards results Study student class IV in subtheme 2 togetherness in diversity of SD Negeri 091254 Batu Onom .

Recommendations

Based on research that has been researcher do it , the advice given study in accordance results research conducted by research _ that is as following :

1. suggestions for school

School should considering the Problem Based Learning model used in learning For develop ability and guidance participant educate to be more maximum from learning before using the Problem Based Learning model.

2. good for teachers

In the learning process teachers can apply the Problem Based Learning model to create an atmosphere learning students in class can more active For disclose what students _ know and get maximum results _ so that learning No teacher- centered .

3. suggestions for student

Student in the Problem Based Learning model you can disclose everyone 's opinion child in give answer answer what students _ know . So that students No bored and more concentrate on the moment learning taking place .

4. suggestions for researcher

Researcher This can become base For develop researchers in the future coming to be implemented _ to students .

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